

Pesticide Formulation by Benzimidazoles Precursors, Phenyl Pyrazole and Strobilurins and its Validation

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INTRODUCTION:

Pesticide is a chemical or biological compound or agent (such as a virus, bacterium, or fungus) that deters, incapacitates, kills, or otherwise discourages pests. Target pests includes insects, plant pathogens, weeds, molluscs, mammals, fish, nematodes (roundworms) and microbes that destroy property, cause nuisance, or spread disease, or are disease vectors. Apart from that some pesticides have benefits; some also have drawbacks, such as potential toxicity to humans and other species and living things.

Pesticide Formulations

A pesticide formulation may comprise of:

- The pesticide active ingredient (A.I.) which controls the target pests;
- The carrier, such as an organic solvent or mineral clay, etc;
- Surface-active ingredients, such as stickers and spreaders; and/or
- Other ingredients, such as stabilizers, dyes and chemicals that improve or enhance pesticidal activity i.e. efficacy and efficiency of product.

Pesticide active ingredients have a range of solubility's. Some dissolve readily available in water, others only in oils. Some active ingredients may be relatively insoluble in either water or in oils. Solubility properties and use of the pesticide generally define which formulations were best deliver the active ingredient.

Seed Treatment

Chemical or biological substances that are applied to seed or vegetative propagation materials to control disease organisms, insects, or other pests are known as seed treatment. Bactericides, fungicides and insecticides are used in seed treatments. Most Seed treatments are applied directly to true seeds, such as corn, wheat or, soybean, which have a seed coat surrounding an embryo. Also

some seed treatments can be applied to vegetative propagation materials such as bulbs, corms or tubers (such as potato seed pieces).

Application of growth regulators, micronutrients and nitrogen-fixing Rhizobium and Bradyrhizobium inoculants are not included in seed treatment, because they are not intended for pest control.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Rao. T. N. et.al (2012): Developed and validate a simple, sensitive and inexpensive method using matrix solid-phase dispersion (MSPD), together with High Performance Liquid Chromatography for determination of strobilurin fungicides residues (Azoxystrobin, Picoxystrobin, **Strobilurins** and Trifloxystrobin) in tomatoes. Extraction after MSPD analysed on HPLC equipped with RP-C18 (PhenomenexLunaC18) column 250mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m column, mobile phases A and B were Acetonitrile and 0.1% formic acid in 70:30 v/v, flow rate is 1.0ml/min and detection at 240 nm by external standard method. Method is useful for regular monitoring of strobilurin fungicide residues.

Cid Y.P. et.al (2012): Developed and validate a fast and efficient method for the determination of **Phenyl pyrazole** in bovine plasma. Samples were subjected to solid-phase extraction (SPE) followed by reversed phase liquid chromatography (LC) separation, using acetonitrile: water (60:40 v/v) as the mobile phase with a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and ultraviolet (UV) detection at 210 nm. Ethiprole was used as the internal standard (IS). The chromatographic separation was performed using a Symmetry C18 column (5 μ m, 4.6 $\times$ 250 mm) preceded by a Kromasil C18 (5 μ m, 4.6 $\times$ 10 mm) guard column. The method was successfully applied to monitor plasma concentrations following subcutaneous administration of Phenyl pyrazole in cattle.

Chen H. et.al (2014): Developed a rapid method has been developed for the determination of **Benzimidazoles precursors** and its metabolite carbendazim in tea samples using ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography tandem mass. Dispersive solid-phase extraction was optimized and employed as a sample preparation technique without concentration and solvent exchange. Separation was carried out using an Acquity Ultra-Performance LC system equipped with an Acquity UPLC HSS T3 column 100mm x 2.1 mm ID, 1.8 μ m particle size. The mobile phase consisted of water (A) and methanol (B) each containing 0.1% formic acid (v/v) using a gradient elution. The flow rate, column temperature and injection volume were 0.25 mL min. 4°C, and 3 mL, respectively. MS equipped with ion-spray interface operated in positive mode was employed for the MS/MS analysis working in multiple reaction-monitoring modes (MRM).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

BENZIMIDAZOLES PRECURSORS

Benzimidazoles precursors is Fungicide, wound protectant

Structure of Benzimidazoles precursors

Mode of action: Benzimidazoles precursors are Systemic fungicide having protective and curative action which is absorbed by leaves and roots of plants.

Uses: This fungicide is effective against a wide range of fungal pathogens, including: eyespot and other diseases of cereals; scab on apples and pears; Can also be used on peanuts, soya beans, almonds, tea, coffee, tobacco, citrus fruit, mulberries, sugar cane, and many other crops. Also, can be used additionally as a wound protectant for pruning cuts on the trees.

PHENYL PYRAZOLE

Phenyl pyrazole is insecticide

Structure

Mode of action: Phenyl pyrazole is Broad-spectrum insecticide which toxic by contact and ingestion. Used to control insects when applied on a soil or for seed treatment.

Uses: for control of multiple species of Thrips on a broad range of crops by foliar, soil and seed treatment. Useful for control of Corn rootworms, Wireworms and Termites by soil treatment in maize, plant bugs on cotton, Diamond-back moths on crucifers, and Colorado beetle on potatoes. Can also be used for Control of Stem borers, Weevils in rice, Leaf miners, leaf folders/rollers and Plant hoppers.

STROBILURINS

Strobilurins is strobilurin type of fungicide.

Structure

Received: 12 October 2023

Revised: 23 October 2023

Final Accepted 4 November 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10071619>

Strobilurins is fungicide with protectant, curative and translaminar properties.

Uses: Strobilurins used for control of major plant pathogens in peanuts, soya beans, grapes, potatoes and tomatoes, bananas

AIMS OF THE RESEARCH WORK:

Perform forced degradation study (Stress study) of Benzimidazoles precursors, Phenyl pyrazole and Strobilurins under stress condition on formulation sample.

Table: 1 Composition of sample to be prepared

S. No.	Ingredients	Composition		Specific Gravity
		g/l(mg/ml)	%m/v	
1	Benzimidazoles precursors	225	22.5	1.22
2	Phenyl pyrazole	250	25.0	
3	Strobilurins	25	2.5	
4	Other ingredients	713	71.3	

Table 2: Reagents and Chemical used

Sr. No	Reagents/Chemicals	Grade	Make
1	Acetonitrile	HPLC	Fischer Scientific, Mumbai
2	Water	HPLC	Mili-Q-Milipore(Merck)
3	Ortho Phosphoric Acid (88%)	AR	Merck
4	Sodium Hydroxide Pellets	AR	SD Fine Chemicals
5	Hydrochloric Acid (35%)	AR	SD Fine Chemicals
6	Hydrogen Peroxide	AR	SD Fine Chemicals

FORCED DEGRADATION STUDY (STRESS STUDY)

In order to determine the stability indicating power of analytical method for quantification of Benzimidazoles precursors, Phenyl pyrazole and Strobilurins, the various stressed conditions to be conduct for forced degradation studies. Regulatory guidance in ICH Q2A, Q2B, Q3B all require the development and validation of stability indicating potency assays. The used forced degradation conditions, stress agent concentration and times of stress, were found to effect degradation,

preferably not less than 1% and not complete degradation of active materials (1-20%). These conditions were fixed on the basis of trial and error.

The degradation sample was prepared by transferring about 100 mg of sample in 50 ml volumetric flask and employed to acidic, alkaline and oxidant media for mentioned time and diluted to volume with diluent and injected. (Acidic and Alkaline condition requires neutralization step before diluting) As such sample was exposed to thermal and photolytic stress condition (sunlight), Sample solution was prepared by taking around 100 mg of sample in 50 ml volumetric flask and diluted to volume with diluent.

These sample solutions were filtered through 0.45 μ m nylon syringe filter and injected. The peak purity of Benzimidazoles precursors, Phenyl pyrazole and Strobilurins peak was checked for any interference from peaks from degradation product. Specific degradation conditions were described as follows.

Acidic condition

Acidic degradation study was performed by taking about 100 mg of sample in 50 ml volumetric flask and added 5 ml of 0.1N HCl and kept for 2 hours at room temperature. After 2 hours, sample solution was neutralized with 5 ml of 0.1N NaOH, diluted with diluent and filtered through 0.45 μ nylon syringe filter and injected.

Alkaline condition

Alkaline degradation study was performed by taking about 100 mg of sample in 50 ml volumetric flask and added 5 ml of 0.1N NaOH and kept for 2 hours at room temperature. After 2 hours sample solution was neutralized with 5 ml of 0.1N HCl, diluted with diluent and filtered through 0.45 μ nylon syringe filter and injected.

Oxidative condition

Oxidative degradation was performed by taking about 100 mg of sample in 50 volumetric flask and added 5 ml of 5% H₂O₂ and kept at room temperature for 15 minutes. After 15 minutes sample solution was diluted with diluent and filtered through 0.45 μ nylon syringe filter and injected.

Thermal condition

Thermal degradation was performed by exposing formulation sample at 54°C for 14 days, this study also known as Accelerated Heat Study (AHS). 100 mg of exposed sample taken in 50 volumetric flasks diluted with diluent, sonicate and filtered through 0.45 μ nylon syringe filter and injected. The sample was found to be stable under this thermal condition

Photolytic condition

Photolytic degradation study was performed by exposing sample to sunlight for 14 days. 100 mg of exposed sample was taken in 50 ml volumetric flask diluted with diluent, sonicate and filtered through 0.45 μ nylon syringe filter and injected.

Table 3: Results of Forced degradation study

Received: 12 October 2023

Revised: 23 October 2023

Final Accepted 4 November 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10071619>

Condition	Results(%m/v)					
	Benzimidazoles precursors		Phenyl pyrazole		Strobilurins	
		Degradation		Degradation		Degradation
Initial	22.98	---	24.58	---	2.61	---
Acidic	20.95	2.03	22.00	2.58	2.34	0.27
Alkaline	14.39	8.59	21.86	2.72	2.33	0.28
Oxidative	20.22	2.76	22.92	1.66	2.45	0.16
Thermal	22.94	0.04	24.59	-0.01	2.67	-0.06
Photolytic	23.11	-0.13	24.45	0.13	2.13	0.48

CONCLUSIONS:

A simple, specific and reliable method has been developed for quantification of Benzimidazoles precursors, Phenyl pyrazole and Strobilurins in their pesticide formulation. Stress study showed that all degradation products were well separated from Thiophnate-methyl, Phenyl pyrazole and Strobilurins confirming its stability indicating power. Method validation study showed that the method is specific, linear, accurate, robust and easily reproducible. This method is also useful for quantification of Benzimidazoles precursors, Phenyl pyrazole and Strobilurins in their single or combination formulated products with different strengths and different formulation types. This method can also useful for analysis of environmental samples (soil, water), agricultural products for pesticide residue analysis of same actives but required additional extraction procedure. Hence developed method can be adapted to regular quality control analysis of production samples and stability samples, environmental samples.

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